

A ROBUST METHOD FOR LAYUP OPTIMIZATION OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with optimization of thin-walled composite structures. Lamination parameters and the total laminate thickness, rather than layup angles and ply thicknesses, are used as design variables, thus including any physically possible layup with a minimum of design variables. Optimization of some stiffness based properties, e.g. vibration frequency, can be made convex and local optima are thus avoided. A strength-of-material criterion based on the strain invariants can be added as a constraint, but convexity is generally lost. The method is successfully used to optimize drive shafts, and it is currently applied to a large FRP/sandwich surface effect ship.

1. INTRODUCTION

For structural optimization of thin-walled composite structures, variable layup and thickness at each point plus variable geometry of the whole structure are often desired. Structural optimization of mainly isotropic structures using variable thickness and geometry matured during the last two decades and presently a number of commercial optimization programs are available. Some of these have capabilities to optimize laminated composite materials as well. They tend to use the orientation and thickness of individual plies in a discrete laminate as design variables. Unfortunately this usually leads to optimization tasks plagued with numerous local optima, a setting which is very undesirable. A new approach was thus requested.

Tsai and Pagano [1] derived expressions for the in-plane (A_{ij}), coupling (B_{ij}), and bending (D_{ij}) stiffnesses of thin laminated composites as linear combinations of so-called lamination parameters, see eqs. (1) - (3) below. By using these lamination parameters as design variables the optimization tasks could be significantly improved for a number of reasons. First, there are few parameters – maximum twelve – needed to describe a general layup of the considered material, and all physically possible layups thus simply can be included. However, more important is that the stiffnesses are linear in the design variables. Grenestedt and Gudmundson [2] showed that the range of the lamination parameters is convex, a fact which together with the linearity of the stiffnesses in the lamination parameters result in the desirable property that no local optima exist for e.g. maximization of potential energy (which is a sort of stiffness maximization), maximization of the lowest eigenfrequency, or maximization of buckling load, see Svanberg [3]. Convexity is guaranteed only when layup variables exclusively are used as design variables, i.e. local thickness and structural geometry are fixed.

There are a few drawbacks with optimization using lamination parameters. First, a general strength-of-material criterion cannot be used since many different layups correspond to each set of lamination parameters. Rather, a strength-of-material criterion based on the invariants of strain has been used. Second, the range of the lamination parameters is as of yet not fully known. It is known for a fair number of practical cases, e.g. orthotropic laminates [2]. However, the whole twelve-

dimensional range is expected to be determined before long. Last, after the lamination parameters have been found by structural optimization, a practical layup must be determined. This can be done analytically for certain cases, and it is simply done by computer (fitting) for other cases.

2. STIFFNESSES AND LAMINATION PARAMETERS

Tsai and Pagano [1] expressed the stiffnesses (here normalized) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{11}^* &= U_1 + U_2 \xi_1^A + U_3 \xi_2^A, & A^{1111} &= A_{11}, & A^{1212} &= A_{66}, \\
 A_{22}^* &= U_1 - U_2 \xi_1^A + U_3 \xi_2^A, & A^{1112} &= A_{16}, & A^{1222} &= A_{26}, \\
 A_{12}^* &= U_4 - U_3 \xi_2^A, & A^{1122} &= A_{12}, & A^{2222} &= A_{22}, \\
 A_{66}^* &= \frac{1}{2}(U_1 - U_4) - U_3 \xi_2^A, & A^{ijkl} &= A^{jikl} = A^{klij}, \\
 A_{16}^* &= \frac{1}{2}U_2 \xi_3^A + U_3 \xi_4^A, \\
 A_{26}^* &= \frac{1}{2}U_2 \xi_3^A - U_3 \xi_4^A,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{11}^* &= U_2 \xi_1^B + U_3 \xi_2^B, & B^{1111} &= B_{11}, & B^{1212} &= B_{66}, \\
 B_{22}^* &= -U_2 \xi_1^B + U_3 \xi_2^B, & B^{1112} &= B_{16}, & B^{1222} &= B_{26}, \\
 B_{12}^* &= -U_3 \xi_2^B, & B^{1122} &= B_{12}, & B^{2222} &= B_{22}, \\
 B_{66}^* &= -U_3 \xi_2^B, & B^{ijkl} &= B^{jikl} = B^{klij}, \\
 B_{16}^* &= \frac{1}{2}U_2 \xi_3^B + U_3 \xi_4^B, \\
 B_{26}^* &= \frac{1}{2}U_2 \xi_3^B - U_3 \xi_4^B,
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{11}^* &= U_1 + U_2 \xi_1^D + U_3 \xi_2^D, & D^{1111} &= D_{11}, & D^{1212} &= D_{66}, \\
 D_{22}^* &= U_1 - U_2 \xi_1^D + U_3 \xi_2^D, & D^{1112} &= D_{16}, & D^{1222} &= D_{26}, \\
 D_{12}^* &= U_4 - U_3 \xi_2^D, & D^{1122} &= D_{12}, & D^{2222} &= D_{22}, \\
 D_{66}^* &= \frac{1}{2}(U_1 - U_4) - U_3 \xi_2^D, & D^{ijkl} &= D^{jikl} = D^{klij}, \\
 D_{16}^* &= \frac{1}{2}U_2 \xi_3^D + U_3 \xi_4^D, \\
 D_{26}^* &= \frac{1}{2}U_2 \xi_3^D - U_3 \xi_4^D,
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

in an orthogonal curvilinear coordinate system. Above, $A^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$, $B^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$, and $D^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ are the physical components of the corresponding tensors, and U_i are material constants of a ply. The normalization is

$$A_{ij}^* = A_{ij} / h, \quad B_{ij}^* = 4 B_{ij} / h^2, \quad D_{ij}^* = 12 D_{ij} / h^3. \tag{4}$$

ξ_i^A , ξ_i^B , ξ_i^D are the twelve lamination parameters

$$\begin{aligned}
 \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta, \cos 4\theta, \sin 2\theta, \sin 4\theta] dz^*, \\
 \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^B &= \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta, \cos 4\theta, \sin 2\theta, \sin 4\theta] z^* dz^*, \\
 \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^D &= \frac{3}{2} \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta, \cos 4\theta, \sin 2\theta, \sin 4\theta] z^{*2} dz^*,
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $z^* = 2z/h$ is the normalized through-the-thickness coordinate and h is the laminate thickness. The material in all plies must be the same (inter-laminar hybrids are not allowed, but intra-laminar are acceptable). In this paper, the lamination parameters ξ_i^A , ξ_i^B , ξ_i^D are used as design variables for the layups of the structures.

3. SOME CONCAVE OBJECT FUNCTIONS

Grenestedt and Gudmundson [2] showed that the range of the lamination parameters is convex. For optimization of thin-walled composite structures, it is often desirable to vary the layup and thickness at each point plus the geometry of the whole structure. If the geometry of the structure and the thickness at each point is fixed (not necessarily the same), the stiffnesses are linear in the design variables. Optimization of the potential energy (which is an optimization of the structural stiffness), the lowest vibration frequency, and the buckling load then result in convex optimization tasks, Svanberg [3] and Grenestedt and Gudmundson [2]. In Figure 1 some simple examples – orthotropic rectangular simply supported plates with constant thickness and constant layup – are presented. The object functions for these depend only on two lamination parameters, ξ_1^D and ξ_2^D , whose range is

$$\xi_2^D \geq 2\xi_1^{D2} - 1, \quad |\xi_1^D| \leq 1. \quad (6)$$

Figure 1. Examples of object functions versus the lamination parameters ξ_1^D and ξ_2^D for simply supported orthotropic rectangular plates. From left to right and top to bottom: potential energy for static deformation for uniformly distributed surface load and plate aspect ratio $a/b=1.3$, squared vibration frequency (ω^2) for $a/b=1.3$, buckling load during uniaxial compression (N^{11}) for $a/b=1.3$, and buckling load during shearing (N^{12}) for $a/b=1.7$.

4. STRENGTH-OF-MATERIAL CRITERION

The strength of composite material plies strongly depends on the orientation of the plies relative to the stress field. However, the longitudinal failure *strain* is for engineering structural materials usually of the same order as for example the transverse failure strain. An approximate failure criterion can be based on the invariants of the strain tensor, thus the strength of the composite will be independent of the rotation of the strain field. Tsai and Hahn [4] dwelled upon such a criterion which can be used as a conservative first-ply-failure approximation. For a failure criterion based on the invariants of the strain tensor, lamination parameters can be used. In the aircraft industry it is common to use the maximum absolute value of the strain in any *fiber* direction as a failure criterion, e.g. limiting the maximum fiber strain to 0.43%. A conservative approximation of this criterion is to limit the maximum absolute value of the (principal) strain to the same limit, in this case 0.43%. The latter criterion has successfully been used together with lamination parameters in for example design of drive shafts. The allowable strain may for example be determined from compression-after-impact (CAI) tests.

5. OPTIMIZATION OF DRIVE SHAFT

Thin-walled orthotropic composite drive shafts are optimized. The structural weight is to be minimized when critical rotation speed, torsional buckling moment, strength-of-material, and torsional stiffness are constrained. The strength-of-material criterion sets a limit on the maximum principal strain, which for an orthotropic shaft subject to torsion is equal to the shear strain, γ_{\max} . The design variables are radius, wall thickness, and four lamination parameters, ξ_1^A , ξ_2^A , ξ_1^D , and ξ_2^D . A computer program, using the method of moving asymptotes (MMA) algorithm, is developed for the numerical optimization.

As bench marks, composite tail rotor drive shafts for helicopters have been considered. By purely changing from aluminum to quasi-isotropically laid-up graphite/epoxy (T300/5208) and using the same dimensions, the weight of the composite shaft becomes 40% less than that of a conventional aluminum drive shaft. Through optimization the weight could be further decreased and depending on loading the weights of composite shafts usually became 50-65% less than those of conventional aluminum drive shafts. The maximum allowed shear strain $\gamma_{\max} = 0.5\%$ was used for both the composite and the aluminum shafts.

6. LARGE SURFACE EFFECT SHIP

This project deals with a number of structural challenges of large surface effect ships (SESSs), see Figure 2. At this point very few results can be presented but some of the problems will be discussed. A major dilemma is the low torsional rigidity of the whole ship. This in combination with the great width results in unacceptable deformations during operation in high seas. One of the optimization tasks is to increase the lowest torsional vibration frequency. The structure is made of FRP sandwich and it is analyzed using sandwich-type finite elements. In these the sandwich skins are subject to pure membrane deformation. By using lamination parameters for the skins, the sandwich stiffnesses become linear in the lamination parameters and thus convexity is guaranteed for fixed thickness designs when for example the lowest vibration frequency is to be maximized. Thicknesses were included as design variables and thus convexity was lost, but the convergence still proved to be smooth. In order to extract the torsional frequency, half the model with anti-symmetric boundary conditions along the center line was analyzed. The longitudinal stiffnesses in both the vertical and horizontal planes should be constrained as should local material strains. The stiffnesses of hull panels are further constrained by slamming loads. Regions around hatches are optimized separately. This is a delicate problem of great importance; a poor design results in the fact that hatches may not be possible to open in high seas because of extensive deformations of the hatch frames.

Figure 2. The experimental surface effect ship "Smyge" which is a stealth surface attack vehicle of the Swedish navy.

5. CONCLUSION

A strategy for optimization of thin-walled composite structures has been outlined. The main obstacle with layup optimization – numerous local optima – is considerably mitigated. The method is currently introduced in design of large practical engineering structures.

References

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